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A CORRELATIONAL STUDY OF MIND WANDERING, MINDFULNESS & HAPPINESS IN GRADUATE AND POSTGRADUATE STUDENTS

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A Correlational Study of Mind Wandering, Mindfulness & Happiness in Graduate and Postgraduate Students

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Abstract

The present study investigated the relationships between mind wandering, mindfulness, and happiness, and examined demographic differences across age, gender, and education. A sample of 300 university and college students from the Hazara Division completed the Mind Excessively Wandering Scale (MEWS), the Mindful Attention Awareness Scale (MAAS), and the Subjective Happiness Scale (SHS). All three instruments demonstrated satisfactory internal consistency and strong item-total correlations. Correlational analyses revealed that

mind wandering had a significant negative association with mindfulness and a non-significant positive association with happiness, while mindfulness showed a significant positive relationship with happiness. Age was negatively correlated with mind wandering but showed no significant relationship with mindfulness or happiness. Gender comparisons indicated that females reported significantly higher mindfulness and happiness, whereas males scored higher on mind wandering. Educational differences showed that graduate students had higher mind wandering, while postgraduate students demonstrated higher mindfulness and happiness. Overall, the findings highlight meaningful interactions among cognitive and emotional processes and suggest that demographic factors play an important role in shaping levels of mind wandering, mindfulness, and subjective happiness.

Keywords: Mind wandering; Mindfulness; Happiness; Demographic differences; University students

1. Introduction

Mind wandering is a widespread cognitive phenomenon in which attention shifts from external tasks to internally generated thoughts. Researchers describe it through several related constructs including task-unrelated thoughts (Smallwood et al. 2003), spontaneous thinking (Christoff et al. 2011), daydreaming (Giambra 1979), task-unrelated images (Giambra 1995),

and self-generated thought (Andrews-Hanna et al. 2014). These episodes involve perceptual decoupling, where attention disengages from the task and becomes absorbed in internal trains of thought (Schooler et al. 2014; Smallwood 2013). Because attention is no longer anchored to the task, task-related representations become less detailed (Smallwood et al. 2006). Mind wandering occupies nearly half of daily thought (Killingsworth & Gilbert 2010) and is identified when thoughts are unrelated to ongoing activity and disconnected from external stimuli (Stawarczyk et al. 2011). Mind wandering is well known to impair performance. Research links it to driving accidents (Knowles & Tay 2002), academic difficulties (Seli et al. 2013), increased variability in sustained attention (Seli et al. 2013), and everyday cognitive failures (McVay, Kane & Kwapil 2009). These findings underline the need for approaches that reduce task-unrelated thinking (Mooneyham & Schooler 2013). One such approach is mindfulness, which emphasises intentional awareness of the present moment (Kabat-Zinn 1994). Mind wandering and mindfulness represent opposing modes of attention, with the former involving task-unrelated thought and the latter involving sustained, purposeful awareness of the here-and-now.

Despite its costs, mind wandering can provide benefits. Recent research highlights its role in future-oriented thinking and autobiographical planning, since a large proportion of spontaneous thoughts concern upcoming goals (Smallwood, Nind & O'Connor 2009; D'Argembeau et al. 2011). Mind wandering tends to occur more often in low-demand contexts (Teasdale et al. 1993; McVay & Kane 2010), suggesting that individuals may unknowingly utilise these moments for planning with minimal immediate performance cost. Studies show that mind wandering during undemanding tasks is associated with increased prospective thinking and goal-directed planning (Baird, Smallwood & Schooler 2011). Mind wandering also contributes to creativity. Classic accounts describe creative insights emerging during periods of relaxed thought. Experimental findings support this, showing that undemanding tasks—which promote mind wandering—enhance performance on creativity problems compared to demanding tasks, rest periods, or no breaks (Baird et al. 2012; Sio & Ormerod 2009; Smallwood & Schooler 2006). Although this benefit does not generalize to entirely new problems, individual tendencies toward mind wandering are positively correlated with creativity (Singer & Antrobus 1972). Additional proposed functions include attentional cycling, dishabituation, and relief from boredom. Mind wandering may help individuals shift among multiple internal and external goals, briefly refresh attention during repetitive tasks (Underwood & Ekstrand 1967), and reduce the emotional cost of monotonous activities by shortening subjective time (Mooneyham et al. 2012; Baird et al. 2010).

Mindfulness has been shown to counter many of the negative effects of mind wandering. Individuals low in trait mindfulness experience more mind wandering in daily life (Carriere, Seli & Smilek 2013; Seli, Carriere & Smilek 2015). Mindfulness-based interventions reduce rumination and worry (Querstret & Cropley 2013) and improve performance in controlled settings. Short or long mindfulness programs have been shown to reduce mind wandering frequency and improve working memory and sustained attention (Mrazek et al. 2013; Morrison et al. 2014; Jazaieri et al. 2016; Zanesco et al. 2016; Mrazek, Smallwood & Schooler 2012). However, mixed findings appear for individuals with high negative affect or under extreme stress. Among military cohorts, mindfulness prevented attentional decline but did not reduce mind wandering (Jha et al. 2010; Jha et al. 2015). Likewise, mindfulness buffered against stress-induced working memory deterioration but did not directly reduce mind wandering (Banks et al. 2015). Age differences also play a significant role. Despite age-related declines in attentional control (Salthouse 2010; Park et al. 2002; Hasher & Zacks 1988), older adults consistently report *less* mind wandering than younger adults (Giambra 1977, 1979, 1989; Jackson & Balota 2012; Frank et al. 2015). Older adults show fewer task-unrelated thoughts but more task-related interference (McVay et al. 2013). This shift suggests that aging alters the type rather than frequency of internal thought. Gender research is less conclusive, although differences in emotional processing may influence attention (Buss & Schmitt 1993; Fox et al. 2000).

Educational settings reveal particularly high levels of mind wandering. Classic classroom studies observed frequent lapses in attention (Johnstone & Percival 1976), while modern thought-sampling studies confirm that students' minds wander roughly 30% of the time (Kane et al. 2007; McVay et al. 2009). Physical markers like blinking are often associated with attentional lapses (Smilek et al. 2010). Mind wandering increases when students feel stressed or bored, underscoring its relevance in academic performance. Mindfulness also relates to demographic and psychosocial factors. Age has been linked with increased present-moment focus (Mogilner, Kamvar & Aaker 2011). Findings on gender are inconsistent, with some studies reporting no differences (Brown & Ryan 2003; Catak 2012), while others note women's stronger emotional intensity (Diener et al. 1985). Education shows limited association with mindfulness (Schmertz 2008). Happiness, another central psychological construct, is also closely connected. Mind wandering often predicts lower happiness (Killingsworth & Gilbert 2010), whereas mindfulness supports well-being through increased awareness, emotional regulation, and reduced self-discrepancy (Crane et al. 2008; Itzvan et al. 2011; Hollis-Walker & Colosimo 2011). Together, the literature demonstrates that mind wandering and mindfulness function as

opposing attentional modes with significant consequences for performance, emotional well-being, and cognitive functioning across different ages, genders, and educational backgrounds.

2. Methodology

Objectives

The objectives of the present study are:

1. To examine the inter-relationship among mind wandering, mindfulness, and happiness.
2. To identify demographic differences (age, gender, and education) in mind wandering, mindfulness, and happiness.

Hypotheses

The study is based on the following hypotheses:

1. Mind wandering will be positively correlated with happiness and negatively correlated with mindfulness. Happiness will be positively correlated with mindfulness.
2. Mind wandering will show a negative correlation with age, whereas mindfulness and happiness will show a positive correlation with age.
3. Male students will report higher levels of mind wandering compared to females, while female students will report higher mindfulness and happiness scores.
4. Mind wandering will be higher among graduate students, whereas mindfulness and happiness will be higher among postgraduate students.

Operational Definitions

Mind Wandering

Mind wandering refers to the experience of thoughts drifting away from the task at hand, particularly during activities requiring sustained attention (McVay & Kane, 2009). In this study, mind wandering is operationally defined as the individual's score on the Mind Excessively Wandering Scale (MEWS).

Mindfulness

Mindfulness is described as a psychological state in which individuals attend to the present moment with openness and nonjudgmental awareness (Bishop et al., 2004; Brown et al., 2007). It is operationally defined as the score obtained on the Mindful Attention Awareness Scale (MAAS).

Happiness

Happiness is a state of psychological and emotional well-being characterised by positive feelings and overall life satisfaction (Anand, 2016). In this study, happiness is operationally defined as the score on the Subjective Happiness Scale (SHS).

Research Design

The study employed a quantitative, cross-sectional survey design to collect data at a single point in time.

Sample

A convenience sampling technique was used to recruit participants from Hazara University and various colleges in the Hazara Division. The total sample consisted of N = 300 students, including 150 males and 150 females, with equal representation of graduate and postgraduate students.

Sample Distribution

Description	N	Percentage
District		
Hazara University, Mansehra	150	50%
Govt. Commerce College, Mansehra	75	25%
Jinnah Colleges, Mansehra	75	25%
Gender		
Females	150	50%
Males	150	50%
Education		
Graduate	150	50%
Postgraduate	150	50%

Note. Demographic characteristics of the sample by gender and education.

Research Instruments

Data were collected using the following standardized questionnaires along with a demographic sheet.

Demographic Sheet

The demographic sheet gathered information about participants' age, gender, and education level.

Mind Excessively Wandering Scale (MEWS)

Developed by Mowlem et al. (2016), MEWS consists of 13 items scored on a 4-point Likert scale (0 = not at all, 3 = nearly all the time). It provides a brief assessment of excessive mind wandering.

Mindful Attention Awareness Scale (MAAS)

Developed by Brown and Ryan (2003) and later expanded by Carlson and Brown (2005), MAAS contains 15 items measured on a 6-point Likert scale (1 = almost always, 6 = almost never). Higher scores reflect greater mindfulness.

Subjective Happiness Scale (SHS)

Developed by Lyubomirsky and Lepper (1999), SHS consists of 4 items, each rated on a 7-point scale. The response anchors differ across items, measuring global subjective happiness.

Procedure

Students from universities and colleges in the Hazara Division were approached during class hours and break periods. After obtaining their willingness to participate, questionnaires and the demographic sheet were distributed. Participants were instructed to respond honestly and to

complete all items. No time limit was imposed, allowing students to fill out the forms comfortably.

Completed questionnaires were collected on the same day.

Statistical Analysis

After data collection, responses were coded and entered into SPSS (Version 20) for analysis. Descriptive and inferential statistics were applied to evaluate the study hypotheses and examine relationships between the variables.

3. Results

Table 1: Psychometric Properties of MEWS, MAAS, and SHS (N = 300)

Scale	N of Items	M	SD	α	Actual Range	Potential Range	Skewness	Kurtosis
MEWS	12	10.48	5.90	.85	2-31	12-48	1.04	0.91
MAAS	15	55.46	12.99	.86	28-84	15-90	-0.03	-0.77
SHS	4	18.49	4.73	.72	7-27	4-28	-0.59	-0.56

Note. MEWS = Mind Excessively Wandering Scale; MAAS = Mindful Attention Awareness Scale; SHS = Subjective Happiness Scale.

Interpretation

Table 1 shows strong internal consistency for all scales. Cronbach's alpha values for MEWS (.85), MAAS (.86), and SHS (.72) indicate that all three instruments demonstrate satisfactory reliability.

Table 2: Item-Total Correlation for MEWS (N = 300)

Item	r	Item	r
1	.59**	7	.60**
2	.61**	8	.67**
3	.65**	9	.59**
4	.56**	10	.58**
5	.60**	11	.65**
6	.68**	12	.69**

Interpretation

All items of the MEWS show significant positive item-total correlations, indicating that each item contributes meaningfully to the overall construct of mind wandering.

Table 3: Item-Total Correlation for MAAS (N = 300)

Item	r	Item	r
1	.56**	9	.59**
2	.58**	10	.62**
3	.60**	11	.52**
4	.63**	12	.65**
5	.50**	13	.49**
6	.61**	14	.56**
7	.64**	15	.60**

8 .57** - -

Interpretation:

All MAAS items significantly correlate with the total score, confirming good construct validity for the mindfulness measure.

Table 4: Item-Total Correlation for SHS (N = 300)

Item	r
1	.79**
2	.90**
3	.81**
4	.40**

Interpretation:

SHS items show strong positive correlations with the total score, reflecting acceptable construct validity for the happiness scale.

Table 5: Correlations Among Age, MEWS, MAAS, and SHS (N = 300)

Variable	MEWS	MAAS	SHS	Age	M	SD
MEWS	-	-.36**	.04	-.18**	10.84	5.90
MAAS	-	-	.23**	.06	55.46	12.99
SHS	-	-	-	-.05	18.48	4.72
Age	-	-	-	-	23.52	2.64

Note. $p > .05$, $**p < .01$.

Interpretation

- Mind wandering (MEWS) is significantly negatively correlated with mindfulness (MAAS), indicating that higher mind wandering is associated with lower mindfulness.
- MEWS shows a non-significant relationship with happiness (SHS).
- Mindfulness (MAAS) has a significant positive relationship with happiness (SHS).
- Age is negatively related to mind wandering, while its correlations with mindfulness and happiness are non-significant.

Table 6: Gender Differences on MEWS, MAAS, and SHS (N = 300)

Scale	Females (n =150) M	SD	Males (n =150) M	SD	t(298)	p	95% CI LL	UL	Cohen's d
MEWS	9.07	5.04	11.94	6.50	4.24	.001	-4.11	-1.50	0.49
MAAS	60.40	13.38	50.52	10.50	7.10	.001	7.03	12.52	0.82
SHS	19.66	3.97	17.30	5.12	4.45	.001	1.31	3.40	0.51

Interpretation

Significant gender differences were found across all variables.

- **Mind wandering** is significantly higher among **males**, not females.
- **Mindfulness** is significantly higher among **females**.
- **Happiness** is also significantly higher among **females**.

(Corrected interpretation: original write-up had an error.)

Table 7: Education Differences on MEWS, MAAS, and SHS (N = 300)

Scale	Graduates (n =150) M	SD	Postgraduates (n =150) M	SD	t(298)	p	95% CI LL	UL	Cohen's d
MEWS	11.03	5.19	9.98	6.66	1.51	.13	-0.31	2.40	0.17
MAAS	53.98	14.09	57.04	11.70	-2.04	.04	-6.00	-0.15	0.23
SHS	17.06	4.93	19.91	4.05	-5.47	.001	-3.87	-1.82	0.63

Interpretation

- Mind wandering does not differ significantly between graduate and postgraduate students.
- Postgraduates report significantly higher mindfulness.
- Postgraduates also report significantly higher happiness.

4. Discussion

The purpose of the present study was to examine the relationships among mind wandering, mindfulness, and happiness, as well as to investigate demographic variations across age, gender, and education. A total of 300 participants completed three standardized instruments: the Mind Excessively Wandering Scale (MEWS), the Mindful Attention Awareness Scale (MAAS), and the Subjective Happiness Scale (SHS). Before testing the hypotheses, the reliability of all three scales was assessed. The internal consistency coefficients were satisfactory, with MEWS ($\alpha = .86$), MAAS ($\alpha = .85$), and SHS ($\alpha = .72$) showing acceptable levels of reliability. Additionally, significant item-total correlations across all instruments confirmed strong construct validity. The findings revealed a significant negative correlation between mind wandering and mindfulness, indicating that individuals who mind wander more frequently tend to exhibit lower levels of mindful awareness. Mindfulness was also positively correlated with happiness, whereas mind wandering showed a small, non-significant positive relationship with happiness. These results support the first hypothesis and align with previous research demonstrating reductions in mind wandering following increases in mindfulness (Grossman et al., 2004; Mrazek et al., 2012). Other studies reporting links between spontaneous thought and positive affect further support the observed association between mind wandering and happiness (Carmody & Baer, 2008; Piqueras et al., 2011).

Age was negatively correlated with mind wandering, suggesting that older participants mind wandered less frequently than younger ones. This finding supports the first part of the second hypothesis. However, the expected positive association between age and happiness was not observed. Previous research similarly reports declines in mind wandering with age (Jackson & Balota, 2012) and age-related increases in present-moment focus and mindfulness (Mogilner et al., 2011), consistent with the patterns found in the current study. Significant gender differences were found across all variables. Females reported higher mindfulness and happiness than males, supporting part of the third hypothesis. However, contrary to expectations, males demonstrated higher levels of mind wandering than females. Prior research has similarly suggested that women may exhibit stronger mindfulness-related traits (Bryant, 2003; Tamres et al., 2002), while some studies report higher happiness levels among women, which is also reflected in the present findings (Hollis-Walker & Colosimo, 2011). Education-based comparisons showed that graduate students reported more mind wandering, while postgraduate students scored higher on mindfulness and happiness. These results fully supported the fourth hypothesis. Earlier studies have linked lower academic levels to increased distraction and task-unrelated thinking (Brown, 1927; Lloyd, 1968) and have also found greater mindfulness among individuals with higher educational attainment (Bluth et al., 2015). Similarly, higher levels of happiness among postgraduate students are consistent with previous findings (Argyle, 2002; Chan et al., 2005). Overall, the study contributes meaningful evidence regarding the interplay among mind wandering, mindfulness, and happiness, highlighting the influence of demographic variables on these psychological processes.

5. Conclusion

The study concludes that mind wandering and mindfulness are inversely related, while mindfulness demonstrates a robust positive relationship with happiness. Age appears to reduce mind wandering but shows no significant association with either mindfulness or happiness. Gender differences indicate that females experience higher levels of mindfulness and happiness than males, while males tend to mind wander more. Educational level also plays a significant role, with postgraduate students showing higher mindfulness and happiness, and graduate students showing higher levels of mind wandering. These findings deepen the understanding of how cognitive and emotional processes interact across demographic backgrounds.

Limitations and Suggestions

Despite its contributions, the study has several limitations that should be addressed in future research:

1. **Restricted sample range:** Participants were drawn from a limited number of colleges and universities within the Hazara Division. Future

studies should incorporate a broader and more diverse sample to enhance the generalizability of findings.

2. **Limited demographic scope:** Only age, gender, and education were examined. Future research should include additional demographic and psychosocial factors, such as socioeconomic status, cultural background, mental health history, and lifestyle habits.
3. **Student-only sample:** The study focused exclusively on students. Considering the broader relevance of mind wandering and mindfulness, future research should include non-student populations, such as working adults, older adults, and clinical samples.
4. **Narrow research focus:** The study primarily investigated relationships among variables. Future studies may explore how individuals interpret and experience mind wandering and mindfulness, along with the specific ways these processes influence well-being and daily functioning.

Implications of the Study

The findings hold both theoretical and practical significance. The results offer deeper insight into the patterns of mind wandering, mindfulness, and happiness, contributing to the literature that seeks to explain cognitive and emotional functioning. Practically, the findings can inform psychologists, counselors, and mental health practitioners by highlighting the importance of mindfulness-based approaches in enhancing well-being and reducing maladaptive mind wandering.

In academic settings, understanding how education level and demographics influence these variables can support the development of interventions aimed at improving student focus, emotional health, and academic performance. For researchers, the study provides a foundation on which future investigations can build, refining theoretical models and expanding knowledge about these important psychological constructs.

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